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PAPER TITLE

“Numerical evaluation of the influence of lip geometry and non-uniform flows on acoustic reflections coefficients”

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ABSTRACT

Fan flutter in aero-engines can result from the coupling between intake acoustic reflections and fan vibrations, particularly near the acoustic cut-on/cut-off condition, where reflection effects are maximised and can trigger the onset of flutter bite. The phase of the reflected waves is the key parameter in assessing the instability. A classical semi-analytical model, developed by Rienstra and based on complex analysis techniques, is commonly used to compute the characteristics of the reflected waves. This model represents the intake as an annular duct with uniform axial mean flow and captures the contributions from all acoustic modes present in the system. However, real intakes deviate from this idealised case: the Mach number inside and outside the intake is not uniform, and the geometry includes a lip with finite thickness, both of which can affect the acoustic field. The aim of this work is to quantify the limitations of the classical model in predicting reflection coefficients. To this end, high-fidelity simulations of various intake configurations are performed, and a wave-splitting is applied to the acoustic field for comparison with the analytical predictions. Results show that the analytical model maintains

good accuracy across a broad range of conditions. The influence of lip thickness on the reflection coefficients is marginal, whereas deviations from uniform Mach number introduce more pronounced phase differences. This suggests that modifications to the analytical model may be required to improve prediction accuracy while retaining its reduced computational cost.

BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

In recent years, an acoustic feedback mechanism known as flutter bite has received increasing attention in the context of fan configurations [1]. This phenomenon becomes particularly relevant near the stall line, where aerodynamic instability is strongly influenced by acoustic effects. Blade oscillations near a natural frequency generate acoustic waves that are reflected at the intake highlight. Depending on the phase of the reflected wave, determined by propagation along the intake and the inlet reflection, an instability mechanism can be triggered.

The reflection at the intake highlight plays a critical role, as demonstrated in recent studies [2, 3], which used simplified models where the intake is represented as a cylindrical duct. These models yield results that differ significantly from those obtained when intake effects are neglected and only other influences, such as acoustic treatments, are considered [4, 5].

Since the relative phase between the emitted and reflected waves determines the onset of instability, accurately computing this phase is essential for predicting flutter bite. In the aforementioned models [2, 3], reflection coefficients are derived using the work by Rienstra [6] under the assumptions of uniform axial flow and an annular duct with zero lip thickness. As shown in [7, 8], where this reflection model is compared with finite element solutions of the acoustic equations, the estimate provided by Rienstra is generally reasonable, although it remains the most uncertain part of the simplified duct models.

Zhao [9] conducted a preliminary study using four circular intake lips with thickness ratios ranging from $D_{lip}/D = 0.1$ to $D_{lip}/D = 0.96$, in order to investigate the influence of lip thickness on the amplitude ratio of intake reflection coefficients, that is, the ratio between the emitted and reflected wave. For the steady-state computations, the mean flow was obtained

using sea-level static (SLS) boundary conditions at the far-field boundaries. The results showed that the amplitude ratio of the reflection coefficients follows the same trend as Rienstra’s model. However, the amplitude ratio decreases with increasing lip thickness, highlighting the importance of lip geometry and boundary conditions in determining intake reflection behaviour.

To investigate the limitations of the reflection model employed in the flutter-bite analysis of González-Monge *et al.* [3], the present work computes reflection coefficients from high-fidelity CFD simulations of intakes with varying lip thickness and with different Mach flow distributions inside and outside the intake. This aspect is of particular relevance since because Rienstra’s model considers identical axial flow inside and outside the intake. The analysis focuses on the influence of these factors on both the amplitude and phase of the reflected waves, with the aim of informing the development of improved models that better represent realistic intake geometries. The study of the reflected waves is restricted to the cut-on waves, which are the only modes capable of propagating within the duct, although the analytical model provides information for all acoustic modes. As the frequencies related to flutter are typically much lower than those associated with noise, only a single cut-on mode is present in the regime of interest, while the rest are cut-off, which means they decay exponentially.

The paper is structured as follows. First, the computational model and intake geometries considered in this investigation are introduced. The wave-splitting procedure, which is used to extract amplitude and phase information from the CFD solutions by decomposing the unsteady perturbations into acoustic modes based on the eigenmodes of the acoustic equations [10], is then described. Finally, the results of the high-fidelity simulations are presented, with comparisons across different intake configurations, and their accuracy is evaluated against the Rienstra’s analytical model.

TEST CASE DESCRIPTION

Computational Model

The computational model selected for this study is an axisymmetric cylindrical intake geometry, with a cross-sectional view shown in Fig. 1. The model did not include both a central hub and a rotating fan, as the main focus of this paper is analysing the impact of the lip thickness in the reflection coefficients at the highlight. The intake has an inner diameter of $D \approx 1$ m and extends downstream to a total length of $L = 3D$, to ensure stabilisation of the acoustic modes as they propagate along the duct.

Three circular intake lip geometries are considered, each based on an axisymmetric design featuring a straight casing wall and a constant-radius circular lip profile. The lip radii correspond to $D_{lip}/D = 0.01$, $D_{lip}/D = 0.03$, and $D_{lip}/D = 0.09$. Although these intake geometries are not representative

FIGURE 1. SKETCH OF THE INTAKE MODEL WITH DIFFERENT LIP THICKNESSES.

FIGURE 2. COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN WITH GROUND AND FARFIELD BOUNDARIES.

of typical industrial designs, they provide a framework for systematically examining the influence of lip radius.

For the CFD simulations, the intake geometry was placed inside a computational domain with dimensions $25D \times 25D \times 25D$, as shown in Fig. 2. The intake was located equidistant from all the side walls and positioned centrally on the back wall of the domain, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Grid Generation

A structured hexahedral grid was generated using *Ansys ICEM 2023R2*. The intake mesh consists of approximately 21.4, 20.6, and 19.2 million nodes for $D_{lip}/D = 0.01$, 0.03, and 0.09, respectively. The overall mesh sizing and topology of the intake were derived from the authors’ previous work on unsteady crosswind simulations [11, 12] investigating intake acoustics. The intake domain contains 640 azimuthal and approximately 54 radial layers. At the far-field boundaries, the mesh employs a constant expansion ratio of 1.15 to reduce the total node count.

FIGURE 3. COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL REFLECTION COEFFICIENTS FOR THREE DIFFERENT INTAKE THICKNESSES WITH ANALYTICAL RIENSTRA MODEL FOR DIFFERENT NODAL DIAMETERS.

Although all three meshes use the same overall topology, the meshing strategy was adjusted to account for the geometric characteristics of the different lip radii. Fig. 3 illustrates the computational grids generated for thick- and thin-lip intake configurations. In the thick-lip case (Fig. 3a), the relatively large curvature at the intake leading edge (LE) allows for a smoother grid transition from the far field to the intake highlight. In contrast, the thin-lip configuration is more complex: its much sharper curvature requires significantly denser and more localised refinement to better capture the lip geometry. As shown in the inset, the mesh is packed much closer to the lip surface than in the thick-lip case, making grid generation more challenging.

Since the present study aims to compare results with Rienstra coefficients obtained for thin-lip configurations and extend the analysis to thicker lips, the intake walls are modelled as inviscid, following the assumptions for the modelling of the acoustic flow in [6]. Consequently, no boundary-layer mesh was generated for these simulations.

Numerical Solver

Numerical studies are performed using the in-house CFD solver HADES, which is a three-dimensional, time-accurate, compressible, viscous, finite-volume hybrid RANS/LES flow solver for unstructured grids. The flow variables are represented at the mesh nodes, and the numerical fluxes are evaluated

along the grid edges. The solver employs the Spalart–Allmaras (SA) one-equation turbulence model. The solution method is implicit and retains second-order accuracy in both space and time. Unsteady flow fields are computed by solving the unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) equations. The HADES solver has been validated and verified for intake flow separation and ground vortex formation by Chennuru *et al.* [12], as well as for a range of two-dimensional canonical flows and high-speed three-dimensional compressible applications in prior work by He *et al.* [13].

CFD Strategy

Steady analysis In this study, computations are performed for the intake in an isolated configuration (i.e., without the fan). The mean flow within the intake is obtained from steady-state CFD simulations, considering two different boundary condition setups:

1. $M_\infty = M_0$: To maintain the same Mach number inside (M_∞) an outside (M_0) the intake, Riemann invariants are used to impose constant Mach number in the farfield. By maintaining the same back pressure at the intake exit as the atmospheric static pressure, the Mach number inside and outside the intake is kept equal, consistent with Rienstra’s model [6].
2. $M_\infty \neq M_0$: In this case, Sea-level static (SLS) atmospheric conditions are imposed at the far-field inlet boundary, and the static pressure at the intake exit is adjusted to obtain the desired Mach number inside the intake. Here, the flow undergoes variation as it enters the intake, which is different from the assumptions of the analytical model.

The Mach number M within the intake is controlled by varying the static pressure at the intake exit boundary. For a given Mach number, the boundary conditions are held fixed across all intake geometries. Two Mach numbers are examined in this study: $M = 0.2$, $M = 0.4$, for the case with uniform flow. For the remaining cases only $M = 0.4$ is used for investigating different Mach number flow and impact of elliptical lip.

Figure 4 presents the radial distribution of the Mach number computed close to the intake highlight (dotted line in Fig. 1) for the three intake geometries at a steady Mach number of 0.6. The Mach number profiles are broadly similar across the different lip radii, except for a deviation in the upper 20% of the radial span, where the value approaches unity near the intake wall. This discrepancy arises from the turning and acceleration of the flow near the intake lip as the lip radius decreases. Since the Rienstra coefficients are a function of the Mach number in the intake, such deviations may affect the numerical prediction of these coefficients. Therefore, the data for computing the Rienstra coefficients must be extracted at an axial location where the radial Mach number is uniform (or very close to it).

FIGURE 4. Circumferentially averaged radial Mach number profile at different axial locations.

Figure 4 also shows the Mach number profile but now at a distance $x_{ws} = 0.5D$ downstream of the highlight. At this location, the maximum variation in Mach number is for the thickest lip, but is less than $\pm 5\%$, which has been considered acceptable. Therefore, all data required for evaluating the reflection coefficients are extracted at this axial position (x_{ws}).

Unsteady Computations Based on the mean flow solution obtained from the steady simulations, unsteady computations are performed by imposing acoustic perturbations at the outlet boundary, as shown in Fig. 5. This setup mimics the outgoing acoustic waves generated by the vibration of fan blades. The acoustic gust is introduced as a pressure perturbation (Δp) in the form of a spinning wave, defined by a specified nodal diameter m and frequency ω , and it is imposed at the intake exit:

$$\Delta p = dp \times \left(\sum_{m=1,2,\dots,n} \sin(m\theta - \omega t) \right) \quad (1)$$

The magnitude of the unsteady pressure perturbation (Δp) is less than 1% of the static pressure at the intake exit boundary. By introducing this spinning-wave as a boundary condition, all radial modes corresponding to a given nodal diameter are excited. Since, within the frequency range relevant for flutter,

FIGURE 5. SPINNING WAVE IMPOSED AT THE INTAKE EXIT

typically only the first radial mode is cut-on while the others are cut-off and rapidly decay, the analysis is restricted to the reflection coefficient of this mode. This coefficient is defined as

$$R_m = \frac{A_R e^{\phi_R}}{A_I e^{i\phi_I}} = \frac{A_R}{A_I} e^{i\Delta\phi} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\phi = \phi_R - \phi_I$ is the phase difference between the reflected and incident waves. Similarly, as illustrated by Fig. 1, A_R and A_I are the amplitudes of the reflected and incident waves.

In this study, reflection coefficients are computed for three different nodal diameters ($m = 1, 2, 3$). For each one, the variation of the coefficients is investigated over a broad frequency range. The imposed acoustic wave propagates throughout the intake until reaching the highlight, where part of it gets reflected from the opening and the rest is radiated outside. This process is studied for all three intake configurations to investigate the influence of lip geometry and non-uniformity of the mean flow on the reflected acoustic waves. The physical time step for the unsteady computations is chosen such that each complete cycle of the acoustic mode is resolved by 200 steps. Consequently, the time step differs for each frequency, and its adequacy was confirmed through a temporal convergence study (not shown here). Finally, a wave-splitting procedure is applied to decompose the unsteady perturbations into the duct propagating modes, from which the amplitude ratio and phase difference of the reflected wave at the intake highlight are obtained.

As an example, a snapshot of the acoustic flow that sets in as a periodic solution is shown in Fig. 6. This plot clearly shows a combination of the upstream and downstream first radial acoustic mode propagating inside the duct, while outside the duct some energy is being radiated. From these results, the wave-splitting procedure explained above can be directly applied at a fixed x location.

Wave-splitting analysis To extract the reflection coefficients from the unsteady CFD solutions, a wave-splitting procedure is employed following the method of Moinier [10]. This approach decomposes the unsteady perturbations inside the

FIGURE 6. FIRST HARMONIC OF THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE IN A MERIDIONAL PLANE SHOWING THE PROPAGATION, TRANSMISSIONS OF ACOUSTIC PRESSURE WAVES.

intake duct into upstream- and downstream-propagating acoustic modes, as well as vortical and entropic modes, by solving a generalised eigenvalue problem derived from the discretised linearised Navier–Stokes equations. The mode splitting is performed by identifying the propagation direction based on the corresponding eigenvalues (axial wavenumbers) and evaluating the amplitude of unsteady pressure and entropy perturbations. For further details on the wave-splitting method, the reader is referred to Ref. [10].

A key input to the wave-splitting procedure is the first harmonic of the solution at the frequency of interest ω , extracted from the unsteady CFD simulation. As the imposed spinning wave propagates upstream, it reaches the intake highlight, where it reflects with a phase shift before travelling downstream back into the duct. The temporal harmonic content at the imposed frequency is removed from the solution, and the wave-splitting is applied at a prescribed axial location x_{ws} to the spatial part of the acoustic wave. At this location, the amplitudes A_{ws} and phases ϕ_{ws} of the cut-on acoustic waves are determined.

Since the Rienstra coefficients are computed at the intake highlight, to make an appropriate comparison, these reflection coefficients computed at x_{ws} are translated to the highlight (x_{ih} , see Fig. 1) by removing the spatial propagation from the inlet highlight to this axial position using the axial wavenumbers of the solution (k_x^\pm). The amplitudes of the outgoing and the reflected cut-on waves for the final periodic solution are constant through the duct [14] (since it is modelled as a cylinder), therefore amplitude ratio (R) is the same. However, the phases of these acoustic waves evolve throughout the duct with a slope given by the corresponding upstream or downstream axial wavenumber. Thus, the phase difference at the highlight is interpolated from the wave-splitting location using the relation

$$\phi_m = \phi_{ws} + (x_{ws} - x_{ih}) \times (k_x^+ - k_x^-) \quad (3)$$

FIGURE 7. STEADY FLOW MACH NUMBER WITH STREAMLINES AROUND THE LIP AT $M_0 = 0.4$ COMPARING CIRCULAR AND ELLIPTICAL LIP FOR THICK LIP (TOP) AND THIN LIP (BOTTOM).

which provides the phase-corrected reflection coefficient at the intake highlight, where k_x^+ and k_x^- are axial wave numbers of the outgoing and the returning waves.

IMPACT OF A CIRCULAR LIP

Same Mach Number Inside And Outside The Intake ($M_\infty = M_0$)

In the first part of this study, the boundary conditions are chosen to be consistent with Rienstra’s model, in which the Mach number in the far field (M_∞) is equal to that inside the intake (M_0). For a given Mach number, the boundary conditions are held fixed across all numerical simulations, independent of the intake geometry.

Figure 7 shows steady-state Mach number contours on the meridional plane ($z = 0$) around the intake lip, with flow streamlines superimposed, for the thin-lip configuration ($D_{lip}/D = 0.01$) and the thick-lip configuration ($D_{lip}/D = 0.09$). Because the Mach number is equal inside and outside the intake, the diameter of the captured streamtube matches the intake diameter in both cases.

Although the thin-lip case appears to exhibit smaller variations in the flow field around the lip, this impression arises from the thicker lip creating greater blockage and thereby enlarging the region of low Mach number. Since this is a local effect, the inset of Fig. 7 highlights the thin-lip configuration, showing a similar contour close to the lip. These results indicate that, despite the different lip radii, the essential features of the stagnation region and flow near the intake highlight remain similar between the two cases.

Figure 8 compares the reflection coefficients—namely the amplitude ratio and the phase of the reflected wave relative to the

incident wave—for $M_\infty = M_0 = 0.2$. The coefficients are plotted as a function of the dimensionless frequency $\tilde{\omega} = \omega D / (2a_0)$ at the intake highlight, where a_0 is the speed of sound of the axial mean flow, for three different intake lip thickness obtained from the numerical simulations. As established in the literature, many factors influence the reflection coefficients an intake, with lip geometry being one of the most important [9]. In this section, reflection coefficients are computed for circular-lip geometries of three thickness and compared against the Rienstra’s analytical model for the circumferential wavenumbers $m = 1, 2, 3$.

Figure 8a shows that resonance ($R_{m,1,1} = 1$) occurs at different $\tilde{\omega}$ for different NDs, corresponding to their respective cut-on ratios (the point at which the first acoustic mode becomes purely propagative). The amplitude of reflection decreases as the frequency increases. Compared to the analytical model, it is clear that the predictions from wave-splitting in the thin lip case agree very well. In addition, the amplitude of the reflection coefficient for all three intake geometries is consistently equal to or lower than the analytical predictions, and decreases further as the lip radius increases. This behaviour can be explained by considering that, in the limit of an infinitely thick lip ($D_{\text{lip}}/D \rightarrow \infty$), the intake reduces to a straight duct with no lip, eliminating reflections entirely. In this case, the amplitude of the reflection coefficient would vanish, meaning that the amplitude ratio of any practical intake must lie between the analytical value and zero. Since the amplitude of the reflected wave remains constant throughout the duct, the value of $R_{m,1,1}$ computed at x_{ws} is identical to that at the intake highlight (x_{ih}). It is also worth noting that at $\tilde{\omega} \approx 0.52$ for $m = 1$, a small rise in the amplitude ratio occurs as the higher-order mode $R_{1,1,2}$ becomes cut-on. This mode is not studied further here, as higher-order modes have negligible influence on the flutter index [2].

Fig. 8b presents the phase of the reflected waves at the highlight relative to the incident wave for the three NDs. As expected, the phase shifts from $-\pi$ to π as the mode transitions from cut-off to cut-on, coinciding with the frequency where the amplitude ratio reaches unity. Beyond the cut-on frequency, the phase increases from $-\pi$ towards $-\pi/2$ before decreasing again as frequency further increases. A slight discontinuity in the phase for 1ND at $\tilde{\omega} \approx 0.52$ is again attributed to the cut-on mode of $R_{1,1,2}$. Since phases evolve along the duct, the values computed at x_{ws} are translated to the intake highlight x_{ih} (using Eq. 3) for direct comparison with the analytical model. The results demonstrate that the predicted phases $\phi_{m,1,1}$ for different lip thicknesses agree closely with the analytical solution and there is a very small influence of the lip thickness on the phases of the reflected wave for $M_0 = 0.2$.

The reflection coefficients for $M_0 = 0.4$ are shown in Fig. 9. The same general trends are observed: the amplitude ratios for the thin-lip configuration are in close agreement with the analytical model, while increasing lip thickness reduces the amplitude ratios for all NDs. Fig. 9b compares the computed

FIGURE 8. COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL REFLECTION COEFFICIENTS AT $M_0 = 0.2$ FOR DIFFERENT INTAKE LIP THICKNESSES WITH ANALYTICAL RIENSTRA MODEL FOR DIFFERENT NODAL DIAMETERS.

phase difference ($\phi_{m,1,1}$) with Rienstra’s model and demonstrates excellent agreement. These results suggest that the influence of lip thickness on the phases predicted by the analytical model is negligible when the Mach number is equal inside and outside the intake. This fact is especially relevant since, to predict the appearance of acoustic-induced flutter, the critical parameter is precisely the phase shift between the reflected and emitted wave.

Since the largest deviations are observed for the thick-lip configuration, all subsequent studies are carried out with $D_{\text{lip}}/D = 0.09$, unless otherwise specified.

Different Flow Inside And Outside The Intake ($M_\infty \neq M_0$)

This part of the study examines the impact of a circular thick-lip configuration under conditions where the Mach number inside and outside the intake differ. The far-field flow is maintained at sea-level static atmospheric conditions ($M_\infty =$

(A) AMPLITUDE RATIO

(B) PHASE

(A) AMPLITUDE RATIO

(B) PHASE

FIGURE 9. COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL REFLECTION COEFFICIENTS AT $M_0 = 0.4$ FOR DIFFERENT INTAKE LIP THICKNESSES WITH ANALYTICAL RIENSTRA MODEL FOR DIFFERENT NODAL DIAMETERS.

0.01), while the Mach number within the intake is significantly higher ($M_0 = 0.4$).

Figure 10a compares the amplitude ratios of the reflection coefficients obtained for the thick-lip configuration with both equal and unequal Mach numbers inside and outside the intake, against Rienstra’s analytical model for three NDs. The results indicate that the amplitude ratio is largely unaffected by differences in Mach number outside the domain. With the exception of a small deviation at $\tilde{\omega} \approx 4$ for $m = 3$, the computed values agree well with those obtained under equal-Mach conditions.

Figure 10b presents the corresponding phases of the reflection coefficients. Here, the phases computed with unequal Mach numbers inside and outside the intake are slightly higher than those from the equal-Mach case, which agree closely with the analytical predictions. These results suggest that while

FIGURE 10. COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL REFLECTION COEFFICIENTS WITH $M_\infty/M_0 = 0.01/0.4$ FOR THREE DIFFERENT INTAKE THICKNESSES WITH ANALYTICAL RIENSTRA MODEL FOR DIFFERENT NODAL DIAMETERS.

differences in Mach number inside and outside the intake have little influence on the amplitude ratio, they do have a measurable effect on the phase of the reflection coefficient.

IMPACT OF A ELLIPTICAL LIP

In this section, the influence of lip shape is examined. In practice, intake lips are not perfectly semi-circular but are generally more elliptical in shape. Such a profile enhances the aerodynamics of the intake by keeping the attached flow as it accelerates and turns around the leading edge. To approximate a realistic lip geometry while maintaining simplicity, a simplified elliptical profile derived from the AIAA workshop [15], and subsequently scaled and adapted in earlier studies by Chennuru *et al.* [11], is adopted in this work.

Figure 11 presents a cross-sectional comparison of the

FIGURE 11. COMPARISON OF SKETCH OF THE INTAKE MODEL WITH THICK CIRCULAR LIP VS ELLIPTICAL LIP.

AIAA elliptical intake with the circular-lip configuration. Both designs share the same inner diameter and intake length up to x_0 ; however, the elliptical intake highlight extends further downstream owing to its shape. Although the outer radius of the AIAA intake is larger than that of the circular design, the local radius of curvature near the lip is smaller, with a smoother gradient along the outer surface of the lip. The steady simulation is performed with SLS conditions in the far field ($M_\infty \approx 0.01$) and a fixed Mach number inside the intake ($M_0 = 0.4$) using the AIAA lip, in order to compare with the circular-lip case. Fig. 12 shows steady-state Mach number contours on the meridional plane ($z = 0$) around the intake lip, with flow streamlines superimposed, for the AIAA lip and the thick circular-lip configurations. Since the Mach number is much lower outside the intake, the external flow is drawn into the intake (creating a bigger streamtube). At first glance, the Mach number distribution around the lip appears similar in both cases; however, the flow around the lip is noticeably smoother for the elliptical lip.

Figure 13 compares the isentropic Mach number distributions along the two intake lips. The arc length s is measured from the intake highlight, such that $s = 0$ corresponds to the highlight location (x_{ih}). For the circular lip, the flow must accelerate more rapidly, reaching a higher Mach number, whereas in the elliptical lip the acceleration is more gradual, leading to a lower suction peak Mach number. It is also observed that, close to the highlight, the local acceleration around the lip causes the Mach number distribution to deviate from the input condition used in Rienstra's model. To ensure consistency, wave splitting is therefore performed at $x_{ws}/D = 0.5$, where the Mach number is uniform at 0.4, as it is seen in the contour plot of Fig. 12. Figure 14a presents the amplitude ratios of the reflection coefficients obtained for the thick-lip configuration and the AIAA lip configuration. It can be seen that there is no very small difference in the amplitude ratios when the frequency is far from cut-off. However, for 3ND at $\tilde{\omega} \approx 4$ there is a big difference. Although more frequencies have to be investigated for this case to draw a general conclusion.

Figure 14b shows the corresponding phases of the reflection

FIGURE 12. STEADY FLOW STREAMLINES AROUND THE LIP AT $M_0 = 0.4$ COMPARING CIRCULAR AND ELLIPTICAL LIP.

FIGURE 13. ISENTROPIC MACH NUMBER PROFILE COMPARING CIRCULAR AND ELLIPTICAL LIP.

coefficients. For all the three NDs there is not difference between different intake lip shapes across all the three frequencies. Therefore, it can be concluded that the shape of the intake lip doesn't seem to be playing a major role in determining the intake reflection coefficients.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study has examined the influence of intake lip geometry and operating conditions on acoustic reflection coefficients using high-fidelity unsteady CFD simulations and a wave-splitting procedure, with results compared against Rienstra's analytical model to explore its limitations. The main findings are summarised as follows:

1. For circular-lip intakes with equal Mach numbers inside and outside the duct ($M_\infty = M_0$), the computed reflection coefficients agree well with Rienstra's analytical model, particularly for the thin-lip configuration. The amplitude of the reflection coefficient decreases as the lip thickness increases, with the largest deviations observed for the thick-lip case. The impact of lip thickness on the phase

FIGURE 14. COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL REFLECTION COEFFICIENTS WITH $M_\infty/M_0 = 0.01/0.4$ FOR ELLIPTICAL INTAKE VS THICK CIRCULAR INTAKE WITH ANALYTICAL RIENSTRA MODEL FOR DIFFERENT NODAL DIAMETERS.

is minimal when Mach numbers are equal. This last assessment regarding the phasing of the reflected wave is particularly important since it is the critical parameter to determine the appearance of the flutter bite instability.

2. When Mach numbers inside and outside the intake differ ($M_\infty \neq M_0$), the amplitude ratios remain largely unaffected, while the phases of the reflected waves exhibit measurable deviations compared to the same Mach number case. This highlights that phase behaviour is sensitive to external flow conditions, whereas amplitude behaviour is more strongly governed by lip geometry.
3. A comparison between the thick circular-lip and the AIAA elliptical-lip configurations shows that the amplitude ratios of the reflection coefficients are essentially identical for the first and second NDs, but noticeable differences appear for

the third ND. However, further frequency points would be required to confirm this trend. The phase results indicate no significant differences across the three NDs, suggesting that the intake lip shape does not play a major role in determining the reflection coefficients.

Overall, the results confirm that lip geometry has an influence on acoustic reflections, with thicker circular lips reducing amplitude ratios relative to analytical predictions, and elliptical lips promoting smoother flow and more realistic intake behaviour. Differences in Mach number inside and outside the intake primarily affect the phase of the reflection coefficient. This is the most important part since the flutter stability of the blade depends mainly on the phase difference of the reflected waves with respect to the incident waves. These insights are relevant for improving low-order acoustic models and for guiding intake design in aero-engine applications. This suggests that refinements to the analytical model are needed to improve accuracy while maintaining reduced computational cost.

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